

The Most Effective Way To Teach In The Direction Of Foreign Education (German Language) Through Problematic Education

G.S. Kinjayevea

Uzbekistan State University of World Languages German Applied Sciences
associate professor of the Department

Abstract: *The article discusses the importance of using problem-based educational technologies in modern conditions and at the same time developing the student's ability to think independently, critically and creatively, creative assimilation of knowledge, skills and abilities as a result of active independent activity, as well as the development of mental activity, problem solving, general information about the situation, characteristics of problematic activities.*

Keywords — logical thinking, critical thinking, potential, innovative competence, scientific research, social, constructive, artistic expression, problem situation, logic, conflict, obstacle, harmony of activity, integrated approach, intellectual activity.

INTRODUCTION.

At the root of the reforms carried out in the educational system of our country, the initiative in professional activities, barkomol is being promoted as the most important problem for the education of the younger generation. As a pedagogical concept, it is possible to consider our approach on the analysis of pedagogical-psychological aspects of the development of educational competence of Foreign Language teachers.

In the development and justification of the mechanism for the development of educational-cognitive competencies of future German language learners by means of problematic educational technologies, it is important to develop in education on the basis of innovative-interactive methods and pedagogical technologies. In particular, the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, during his visit to the Andijan region on February 1, 2023, stopped at the issue of youth, saying that “those who graduate without a profession have difficulty in life, do not find a job.

Today, in order for our Republic to take a worthy place among the world's progressive countries, it requires changing the worldview of young people, forming them as strong-willed, knowledgeable and potential, meeting the requirements of modern scientific and technological progress.

Today's education, which is developing rapidly, has made it a task for society to educate young people with strong immunity, responsive to World traditions, innovative-competent, special abilities, targeted ones. It is the problematic educational technology that plays a leading role in solving these tasks.

Problem education is an operation of logical thinking. It is an education that serves to form skills and competencies in students, such as creative search, the implementation of small studies, the promotion of certain hypotheses, the justification of results, the arrival of certain conclusions. Problem education is a new system of formation of the student's scientific knowledge and concepts, worldview, comprehensive improvement of his intellectual activity, the development of

the student's ability to think and the formation of his beliefs, relying on didactics.

The pedagogical and psychological aspects of the concept of the development of educational competence of teachers of the German language are touched upon: it is necessary to dwell on the etymological analysis of the concepts of “competence”, “competence”. There have been different interpretations of the concepts of “competence” and “competence” by scholars. By competency approach, avvlo, the word” Competence “comes from the word” to compete“, which means” erudition in one field or another”.

In particular, it is possible to assess the appropriation of the active component of educational competence of teachers of the German language. To do this, it is necessary to model various life situations that require the development of clear visions of the need to act in this situation, which should be assessed not only from the point of view of spiritual-moral, patriotic values, but also from the point of view of the analysis of a particular situation, the point of knowledge directing social, economic, moral, cultural and

On this basis, the participation of mastering degrees in various seminar trainings based on the development of knowledge and skills within the framework of the development of educational qualities of the future teacher in professional situations by stating their opinions and opinions, independent views-until the future call, military education teachers can be considered as having achieved the maximum level of educational competence.

The following tasks play an important role in the organization of the social lifestyle of the higher education institution within the framework of the mechanism for the development of educational competence of future German teachers[38; 104 P.]:

The first ideas of problem education are the American psychologist and educator Dj. It is justified by the Duke (1859-1952) and began to spread in the 20-30s of the XX century .

A.M.Matoshkin, M.I.Makhmutov, I.Ya.The Lerner studied problematic teaching patterns in depth.

Dj.The DUI defines the following areas as the basis of problematic education.

- 1) social;
- 2) constructive;
- 3) artistic expressionism;
- 4) R & D.

Problem education is the most effective way to teach. Today, problem teaching is an active independent activity of a student, aimed at problem situations and their solutions, created under the guidance of an educator in the process of activity. The educator creates a problematic situation, directs the student to solve it, organizes the search for several solutions. Thanks to this, students acquire professional knowledge, skills and abilities, and intellectual thinking skills develop.

The organization of this education is able to effectively apply in practice, management requires a strong pedagogical skill from an educator. Because the emergence of a problem situation is an individual situation and requires an individualized approach.

The basis of problem education is a problem (from Greek “barrier”, “difficulty”) or problem situations. We look at most problem and problem situations in the same way. In fact, they are different from each other.

Problem situations are a mental state in which students face problems in the process of completing certain tasks, realize the conflict that has arisen, an obstacle, which entails the search for a new knowledge of the issue being solved and related to it.

There are certain stages in solving problem situations.

Solving problem situations occurs in the process of problem-based learning. When organizing a problem-based educational process, a pedagogue should pay attention to choosing the right methods, and the methods used are of great importance. The pedagogue should have a complex approach to the successful organization of problem processes.

The success of problem-based learning mainly depends on the following factors:

- problematization of educational material
- activation of cognitive activity of students
- harmonizing the educational process with play and work
- the pedagogue has the ability to effectively use problematic methods in their place
- to create a chain of problematic questions related to the solution of the problem situation and explain it to the students in a logical sequence.

In the process of problem-based education, if attention is paid to the above-mentioned factors, it will affect the formation of students' scientific worldview, active intellectual thinking activities related to the mastering of the students' system of concepts, affect their feelings and emotions, and improve their knowledge. causes it to become a belief. Formation of worldview is formation of intellectual activity of a person.

In conclusion, in today's modern conditions, the use of problem-based educational technologies ensures the effective passing of the educational process and, at the same time, develops the student's ability to think independently, critically and creatively. As a result of active independent activity of students, it allows creative acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities and development of mental activity. Also, if the educational processes of students are organized by the pedagogue, realizing the essence of problem-based education, that is, problem-based teaching, he organizes the management of their cognitive activity by acquiring new knowledge by solving their problems, obstacles and situations. This creates a scientific-research method of acquiring knowledge.

Targeted and effective use of problematic educational technologies by the teacher in the process of teaching is the basis for improving the quality of education and increasing its effectiveness.

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